

Influence of sheath blight (ShB) on agronomic traits at different N levels

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We studied changes in agronomic traits of MTU6024 caused by ShB at 0, 40, 80,

and 120 kg N/ha. Plant samples from a field trial at ARS in 1984 kharif were subjected to split-plot analysis. Main plots were N levels and subplots were healthy and diseased plants. Rice was planted in 3- × 5-m plots at 20- × 15cm spacing and 13 kg P/ha was applied. Agronomic traits of healthy and diseased plants were recorded. ShB increased significantly with each

N level. Plant height, effective tillers per hill, and number of grains per panicle did not differ significantly. Percentage filled grains and 1,000-grain weight were significantly less in diseased than in healthy plants (see table). Although disease score increased with N, there were no consistent changes in agronomic or yield characters. *ℓ*

Effect of ShB on agronomic traits of rice in Maruteru, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Disease score ^a	Plant height (cm)		Effective tillers/hill		Grains/panicle (no.)		Filled grains (%)		1,000-grain weight (g)	
		Healthy	Diseased	Healthy	Diseased	Healthy	Diseased	Healthy	Diseased	Healthy	Diseased
0	5	99	99	8	8	119	126	86	73	23	23
40	6	100	101	9	9	116	114	87	68	23	22
80	7	102	103	9	9	125	125	88	82	23	23
120	7	104	105	9	9	131	117	88	13	24	23
Mean	6	101	102	9	9	123	120	87	74	24	22
CD N × D (0.05)	0.5							7.2		0.7	
CV %	1.2	1.0		3.0		18.3		11.6		4.1	

^aStandard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale.

Effect of inoculum age on transmission of rice gall dwarf virus (GDV)

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GDV-infected TN1 plants were maintained by vegetative propagation through bimonthly cutting, dividing, and transplanting in an airconditioned greenhouse (27 + 3° C).

Inocula of different ages were used for the transmission test and ELISA. Rice plants infected with rice dwarf virus

Table 2. Detection by ELISA of GDV antigens in rice plants at various times after inoculation, Ibaraki, Japan.

Replication	Dilution ^a	Virus concentration			
		0 yr	0.5 yr	1.0 yr	3.0 yr
I	1.600	—	—	—	0.800
II	3.200	—	—	1.600	1.600

^a Reciprocal of the highest dilution with positive reaction.

Table 1. Transmission efficiency of GDV and RDV from plants of different inoculum ages, Ibaraki, Japan.

Virus	Replication	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants (no.)			
			0 yr	0.5 yr	1.0 yr	2.0 yr
GDV	I	50	13	7	8	12
	II	60	31	—	5	9
RDV	I	50	8	2	0	0
		60	6	—	0	0

(RDV), the transmissibility of which is reported to decrease very quickly, were treated in the same manner and results were compared with those with GDV.

GDV transmissibility (Table 1) and virus concentration (Table 2) remained

high for 2 yr. RDV transmissibility decreased very quickly (Table 1). The results indicate that, in favorable conditions, GDV-infected plants may provide inoculum for longer than 2 yr. *ℓ*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Estimating rat damage in deep water rice

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In Bangladesh, rat damage is estimated by quadrat sampling, but the method is not yet reliable for deep water rice. In 1982, we used burrow system density and average amount of stored rice per system to estimate grain loss due to rodents in several deep water areas.

Data on the density of rat burrow systems/ha were obtained in 7 deep water Upa-zillas (subdistricts) by taking a 30-m-wide transect and crossing 10 to 30 fields from the nearest high ground out to 350 m (see figure). Density within the first 25 m was low because those fields are excavated for repairing highways and to build up island-villages. Burrow system density increased from the 26th m and was almost constant to 175 m, but was low between 176–275 m from high ground. Observations indicated that field condition was more important to burrow density than distance to high ground.

At harvest, we collected 23 samples of cached rice from burrow systems. Both large and small burrows contained an average 1.7 kg rice (see table).

Damage varies from Upa-zilla to Upa-zilla. Areas where floods receded first were hardest hit. Low damage and low burrow densities in Ruppangj, Polash, and Narshingdhi reflect their low lying nature. Even at harvest the water table was within 0.25 cm of the surface and some fields had 2–5 cm standing water. Under such conditions, bandicoot rats do not invade the fields, but burrow into the shallow bunds separating fields. Damage was thus minimal. Mean density of burrow systems/ha was 35, mean stored rice was 57.8 kg/ha, and average damage was

Rat damage to deep water rice based upon cached rice in Bangladesh in 1982.

Area	Burrow systems/ha	Estimated ^a stored rice (kg/ha)	% loss ^b from 1012 kg/ha
Manikganj	76	126	12
Manikganj	71	119	12
Manikganj	42	70	7
Mirjapur	60	100	10
Ruppangj	18	30	3
Ruppangj	10	17	2
Polash	21	35	3
Narshingdhi	20	33	3
Daudkandi	27	45	4
Daudkandi	11	19	2
Gazaria	24	40	4
Gazaria	36	60	6
Mean	35	58	6

^a Based on 1.7 kg/system (mean of 23 samples of cached rice). ^b Av national yield/ha of 1982-83 season.

Relation between burrow system density in deep water rice areas and distance from the high ground, Bangladesh, 1982.

5.7% of the crop, although farmers reduced this by collecting cached rice at harvest.

Based on 57.8 kg rice/ha stored by rats, the national loss of deep water rice in 1982 was 89,414 t of paddy.

Traditional pest control practices in West Africa

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Extensive surveys of West African rice farmers, particularly in Sierra Leone, have provided valuable information about pest management practices. Following are some common practices.

Felled tree trunks and other wood remnants are left to help reduce termite damage on rice. When newly cleared fields are completely free of logs, termites feed on rice roots and kill many seedlings.

Before rainy season peaks, soil is mounded so that even when fields are flooded, soil on the mounds remains above water. Weeds emerge and grow. Just before field preparation and transplanting, mounds are broken up and scattered, which kills the weeds. This practice is particularly common in the north, where *boliland* rice farms are located.

Fields are fenced with palm fronds to prevent rodents from entering. Rodents cause major damage in many rice

growing areas in Africa.

In Sierra Leone, a mixture of eight or more rice varieties is planted in traditional upland rice areas. The mixture of varieties reduces damage by insect pests and diseases and provides stable yields. It is common to see rice fields with a mixture of varieties at varying maturity. Some farmers said this practice makes rice available as needed. Bulk storage encourages destructive storage pests such as rice weevils.

Birds are major pests of rice in West Africa; therefore farmers like awned varieties, which lessen bird damage. *Oryza glaberrima* and *O. sativa* indica varieties such as Rok 16 and Ngovie are popular.

In mangrove swamps, farmers plant several rice seedlings per hill to compensate for crab damage. Planting older seedlings also reduces damage.

In a village or town, farmers tend to grow the variety or varieties with similar duration planted at more or less the same time. A variety that matures earlier than others planted nearby will have greater bird damage.

Integrated with other tactics, these simple practices could serve as a basis for effective pest management programs.